

Henryk Górecki's Symphony №3 (Opus 36: 1976)

“Symphony of Sorrowful Songs”

Polish composer Henryk Górecki's *Third Symphony* is a meaningful instance of contemporary orchestral music that attains true victory. After its initial release in 1976, the composition was disregarded and disapproved. However, upon its reissue by Nonesuch in 1992, it achieved unexpected success, surpassing one million copies sold and establishing a precedent for the genre recognised as "holy minimalism." The piece's second movement in question has been utilised in various marketing campaigns, television advertisements, and cinematic productions. It has recently been featured on the newly debuted Classic FM radio station.

Gorecki's Background:

On December 6, 1933, Henryk Gorecki was born in Czernica, a small town in Poland. His paternal figure, a skilled artisan and non-professional instrumentalist, hailed from a humble upbringing. Gorecki's rural upbringing and exposure to folk music and his natural surroundings profoundly impacted the development of his musical style.

Gorecki's early musical education was fostered by his family, who recognised and supported his innate musical talents. The individual in question underwent a period of formal musical education, during

which they received instruction in composition from Boleslaw Szabelski and in conducting from Witold Krzeminski at the State High School of Music in Katowice. Gorecki's musical style exhibits the influence of Karol Szymanowski, a prominent Polish composer renowned for incorporating folk elements into his works.

Poland's political and social milieu influenced Górecki's compositional style during his time. The artist's compositions often reflected the adversities and challenges faced by the populace of Poland while simultaneously expressing a vehement opposition towards the Communist regime. His Third Symphony, the main

subject of this article, is also known as *The Symphony of Sorrowful Songs*. It was composed during political and social turmoil in Poland and resonated deeply with its audience. The work's poignant themes and emotive melodies spoke to the lingering trauma of World War II and the oppressive Communist government.

Gorecki's preference for straightforwardness and austerity in music is evident from his use of close harmonies, minimalistic techniques, and folk melodies. Additionally, notable composers of minimalist contemporary classical music, like Arvo Part and Steve Reich, influenced his musical style.

Gorecki's compositional style is a product of his formative years, education in music, and socio-political milieu, collectively shaping his distinct artistic vision. The composer in question achieved great renown in the 20th century due to his incorporation of folk motifs, utilisation of minimalistic techniques, employment of close harmonies, and exploring political and social issues.

The Symphony of Sorrowful Songs:

The *Symphony of Sorrowful Songs* is a highly acclaimed and beloved composition in contemporary classical music. In 1976, the symphony was composed and later made its debut in Poland in 1977. The composition in question scored for soprano and orchestra, comprises three movements, each of which features a unique text that pertains to a specific aspect of loss, grief, and separation. The English translation of the Polish lyrics is provided at the end of the

article. They are worth reading and contemplating (particularly with the performance provided).

Movement One:

The first movement of the symphony draws inspiration from the Polish lament “Sliczny chłopiec” (Beautiful Boy), a sorrowful vocal piece sung by a woman mourning the passing of her son.

Movement Two:

The second movement centres on a single pitch that Helena Wanda Blazusiakówna, an 18-year-old victim of Nazi persecution and execution during the Second World War, inscribed on the wall of a Gestapo prison cell. The composition of Blazusiakówna’s movement is a prayer to the Virgin Mary, serving as a supplication for guidance and safeguarding during the approach of death. In this musical passage, the soprano soloist delivers the prayer with a plaintive and melancholy tone. This effectively captures the emotional feelings of futility and sorrow that Blazusiakówna may have felt. The passage exhibits a hauntingly beautiful quality.

Movement Three:

The symphony's final movement incorporates a Silesian folk melody originating from the region presently within the borders of Poland. The vocal text of the composition portrays a maternal lament for her offspring, which the ravages of war have taken away. In this movement, the soprano soloist delivers the mother's lyrics with a highly emotive and yearning quality, effectively conveying profound sorrow and absence. The overall effect is a poignant portrayal of mourning and grief.

What Makes This Composition Special?

The Symphony of Sorrowful Songs by Gorecki is a highly dynamic composition that resonates with the universal human experience of grief and melancholy. The hauntingly beautiful composition of the music is effectively expressed through rich orchestration and soaring vocal lines, which convey the emotional impact of the poems. The enduring popularity of the symphony, a beloved work of contemporary classical music, is a phenomenon that audiences can readily comprehend.

The symphony has been a hit with the Royal Philharmonic, as well as many dozens of orchestras around the world, who keep Górecki's work as a regular item in their concert repertoire

It distinguishes itself from the composer's other works through its heightened emotional intensity, approachable musical narrative, and remarkable capacity to elicit intense emotional reactions from its audience, despite the composer's recurrent exploration of themes of grief and affliction. The use of simple, folk-inspired melodies and the melancholy timbre of the soprano soloist imbue this modern classical composition with a relatable and accessible quality, even to those unacquainted with the genre.

The Symphony of Sorrowful Songs distinguishes itself from Gorecki's other works through its emotional expressiveness, ease of

comprehension, and contextual significance. The aforementioned statement attests to the timeless capacity of music to connect with its audience on a profound emotional plane, providing comfort and reassurance during trying or ambiguous times.

Notable Sopranos:

Several notable sopranos, including Dawn Upshaw, Elzbieta Szmytka, and Zofia Kilanowicz, have performed the Symphony of Sorrowful Songs by Henryk Gorecki. Ascertaining the preeminent soprano to have executed the symphony is a formidable task, given that it is primarily a matter of personal preference. In recent performances of the Symphony of Sorrowful Songs, Krzysztof Penderecki conducted renowned sopranos:

— In 2014, Isabel Bayrakdarian performed the symphony alongside the Warsaw Philharmonic Orchestra and Choir under the direction of conductor Penderecki.

— In 2017, Olga Pasichnyk executed the symphony under the baton of Penderecki alongside the National Symphony Orchestra of Ukraine.

— In 2018, the Sinfonia Varsovia Orchestra, under the direction of Penderecki, featured Agata Zubel as the performer of the symphony.

Throughout the years, numerous exceptional sopranos have graced the stage to perform the Symphony of Sorrowful Songs.

Statne divaldo Kosice with the Polish National Radio Orchestra

But, for me, the most hauntingly “accurate” portrayal of grief and melancholy came from another Penderecki collaboration, this time with “pop” star Beth Gibbons, with the London Philharmonic and the Polish National Radio Orchestra in the last ten years (the latter of which I provide further below).

To what extent have they pursued their personal interpretation?

Experts agree that the soprano's performance should conform to the composer's dynamic and notational indications while incorporating personal interpretation and emotional expression. At the same time, the soprano's execution and affective rendition may imbue the music with vitality and captivate the audience, and the composer's musical notation and dynamic indications function as a structural basis for the rendition.

The soprano's performance requires a delicate equilibrium between adherence to the composer's artistic intentions and the manifestation of the performer's personal aesthetic interpretation. Ultimately, the degree of emotional expression conveyed in a soprano's rendition of a piece is a matter of personal interpretation and discretion.

The Rendition of Beth Gibbons' Performance in the Soprano Role:

(Beth Gibbons, a renowned English singer-songwriter, is widely recognised as the primary vocalist of the musical group Portishead. The subject's birthplace is Exeter, Devon, England, and her date of birth is January 4, 1965. Upon the establishment of Portishead, a renowned trip-hop ensemble celebrated for their melancholy and ambient timbre and Gibbons' evocative singing, Gibbons inaugurated her musical vocation during the 1990s. In 1994, the band's inaugural album, Dummy, was met with critical and widespread acclaim, ultimately earning the prestigious Mercury

Prise. Gibbons' collaborative effort with Paul Webb of Talk Talk on the CD Out of Season is noteworthy in addition to his solo projects. Gibbons' vocal prowess is widely acknowledged as exemplary and distinguished within her era. Her contributions to Portishead have significantly impacted the development of alternative and electronic genres.)

Gibbons has performed the soprano role of the Symphony of Sorrowful Songs with the London Philharmonic Orchestra and the Polish National Radio Orchestra under Krzysztof Penderecki. Critics have lauded her performance for its unique and haunting character, achieved through the use of ethereal and otherworldly vocal

qualities. Critics observed that Gibbons' rendition of the composition exhibits a certain degree of restraint in contrast to other sopranos who have attempted it. However, this restraint serves to augment the emotional resonance of the piece.

A group of world-class sopranos, including Stefania Woytowicz, Dawn Upshaw, Zofia Kilanowicz, Christine Brewer, and Susan Gritton, performed the vocal parts in previous recordings of this symphony. A pure and operatic quality characterised their vocal style. Even Megan Stetson, a mezzo-soprano with formal training, executed the vocal performance (with Colin Stetson, an avant-garde saxophonist who incorporated layers of distorted guitars, baritone sax drones, and sludge rock drums in a brave revision of the symphony), but retained her core operatic style despite the post-nouveau arrangement of Gorecki's classic she was delivering.

However, the induction of Beth Gibbons from Portishead into the Górecki Hall of Fame is a remarkable occurrence deserving of attention. Her vocal style deviates significantly from the rigours of operatic singing and is characterised by precise articulation,

powerful projection, and exceptional breath management. Instead, her voice is characterised by a strained, peaceful quality reminiscent of the vocal stylings of Billie Holiday and Shirley Collins.

Gibbons' contralto voice is technically hindered at times when her performance is in the higher soprano range. This results in a restless and uncontrolled vibrato, particularly noticeable in the first movement. As a result, her attempt to imitate critical operatic clichés has been suggested by some as not entirely successful; however, it is my view that the “uncontrolled” vibrato is reminiscent of “uncontrolled” crying in the pain of grief and, as such, she portrays the narrative of the symphony with uncanny accuracy, whether or not it was intended to be such. Conversely, the performer's unadorned and conversational (or colloquial) approach imbues the composition with inextricable human elements.

Her vocal range exhibits a notable affinity for the lower register of the second movement. This section of the piece draws inspiration from a written plea by a prisoner of the Gestapo during the Second World War, which is prominently featured in the composition. The limitations of Gibbons' composition seem to convey the silent despair of the lyrics.

In the third movement, Gibbons' vocal range is stretched. However, this characteristic can be interpreted as an intentional musical choice reminiscent of the style of a Silesian folk ballad. The song's perspective is that of a grieving mother mourning the loss of her son. An awe-inspiring ethereality characterised the preceding renditions;

however, Gibbons' composed and unpretentious delicacy imbues this performance with a disquieting and captivating affective quality.

Enough of my words. Now for some music (but the important words are further below):

Gibbons and the Polish National Radio Orchestra, conducted by Penderecki: **Henryk Górecki's Symphony of Sorrowful Songs (Symphony №3)**

[<https://youtu.be/DoaEEVMrL-g?si=RG0GSqxjgk6WPIJU>]

Words Accompanying Henryk Górecki's Symphony of Sorrowful Songs:

(translation)

First Movement

*My son, my chosen and beloved
Share your wounds with your mother
And because, dear son, I have always carried you in my heart,
And always served you faithfully
Speak to your mother, to make her happy,
Although you are already leaving me, my cherished hope.*

(Lamentation of the Holy Cross Monastery from the "Lysagóra Songs" collection. Second half of the 15th century)

Second Movement

*No, Mother, do not weep,
Most chaste Queen of Heaven
Support me always.*

“Zdrowas Mario.” ()*

(Prayer inscribed on wall 3 of cell no. 3 in the basement of “Palace,” the Gestapo’s headquarters in Zadopane; beneath is the signature of Helena Wanda Blazusiakówna, and the words “18 years old, imprisoned since 26 September 1944.”)

() “Zdrowas Mario” (Ave Maria) — the opening of the Polish prayer to the Holy Mother*

Third Movement

*Where has he gone
My dearest son?
Perhaps during the uprising
The cruel enemy killed him*

*Ah, you bad people
In the name of God, the most Holy,
Tell me, why did you kill
My son?*

*Never again
Will I have his support
Even if I cry*

My old eyes out

*Were my bitter tears
to create another River Oder
They would not restore to life
My son*

*He lies in his grave
and I know not where
Though I keep asking people
Everywhere*

*Perhaps the poor child
Lies in a rough ditch
and instead he could have been
lying in his warm bed*

*Oh, sing for him
God's little song-birds
Since his mother
Cannot find him*

*And you, God's little flowers
May you blossom all around
So that my son
May sleep happily*

(Folk song in the dialect of the Opole region)